

Course notes
for the ICONIP'2007 tutorial

**Introduction to Theory, Construction and
Application
of
Clifford Neural Networks**

by

Sven Buchholz

and

Kanta Tachibana
Eckhard M.S. Hitzer

S. Buchholz, K. Tachibana, E. Hitzer, Introduction to Theory, Construction and Application of Clifford Neural Networks, ICONIP 2007, 14th International Conf. on Neural Information Processing, Japan, 13 Nov. 2007, 14 pp.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Basics of Clifford Algebra	2
3	Clifford Neurons	4
3.1	Basic Clifford Neurons	4
3.2	Spinor Clifford Neurons	6
4	Clifford Multi-layer Perceptrons	8
4.1	Universal Approximation	9
4.2	Back-propagation Algorithm	10

1 Introduction

Clifford neural networks is a handle for neural networks in the Clifford algebra domain. Clifford algebras are named after the mathematician William Kingdon Clifford. They subsume, for example, the real numbers, the complex numbers and the quaternions. The latter being a four-dimensional algebra invented by William Rowan Hamilton. In the 1960s David Hestenes started to study Clifford algebras as a universal language for geometry for which he coined the term "Geometric algebra". A term that actually dates back to Clifford himself. Its geometric nature makes Clifford algebra a very interesting framework for neural computation. These notes are intended to sketch some fundamentals of the theory of Clifford neural computation.

Fortunately, complex-valued neural networks are a vital topic themselves. The recent book [11] provides an overview about their theory and applications.

Quaternionic neural networks are an emerging topic. Their theory started with the pioneering work of Arena *et al.* [1].

2 Basics of Clifford Algebra

An algebra is a real linear space that is equipped with a bilinear product. Clifford algebras are of dimension 2^n ($n \in \mathbb{N}_0$) and are generated by so-called quadratic spaces, from which they inherit a metric structure. Every quadratic space has an orthonormal basis. Here we are interested in spaces \mathbb{R}^{p+q} ($p, q \in \mathbb{N}_0$) with canonical basis $\mathcal{O} := (e_1, \dots, e_{p+q})$ that are endowed with a quadratic form Q , such that for all $i, j \in \{1, \dots, p+q\}$

$$Q(e_i) = \begin{cases} 1, & i \leq p \\ -1, & p+1 \leq i \leq p+q, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$Q(e_i + e_j) - Q(e_i) - Q(e_j) = 0, \quad (2)$$

which, in turn, renders \mathcal{O} to be orthonormal. These quadratic spaces, abbreviated as $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ hereafter, give now rise to the following definition.

Definition 2.1 (Clifford Algebra [17]) *The Clifford algebra $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$ of $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ is the 2^{p+q} dimensional associative algebra with unity $1_{\mathbb{R}}$ given by*

- (i) $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$ is generated by its distinct subspaces \mathbb{R} and $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$
- (ii) $x \otimes_{p,q} x = xx = Q(x)$ for any $x \in \mathbb{R}^{p,q}$.

Note that we will also make use of juxtaposition for the so-called geometric product of $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$. Since nothing new is generated in case of $p = q = 0$, $\mathcal{C}_{0,0}$ is isomorphic to the real numbers \mathbb{R} . The Clifford algebra $\mathcal{C}_{0,1}$ is isomorphic to the algebra of complex numbers. In fact, here e_1 "is" the imaginary unit of complex numbers i (i.e. $e_1 \equiv i$). The algebra $\mathcal{C}_{0,2}$ is isomorphic to the algebra of quaternions as can be seen from its multiplication table 1. How this table results from Definition 2.1 will become clear after the following.

$\otimes_{0,2}$	1	e_1	e_2	$e_1 e_2$
1	1	e_1	e_2	$e_1 e_2$
e_1	e_1	-1	$e_1 e_2$	$-e_2$
e_2	e_2	$-e_1 e_2$	-1	e_1
$e_1 e_2$	$e_1 e_2$	e_2	$-e_1$	-1

Table 1: Multiplication table of $\mathcal{C}_{0,2}$.

The set of all geometric products of elements of \mathcal{O}

$$\mathcal{E} := \{e_{j_1} e_{j_2} \cdots e_{j_r}, 1 \leq j_1 < \dots < j_r \leq p+q\} \quad (3)$$

constitutes a basis of $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$, which follows directly from condition (ii) in Definition 2.1. This basis can be ordered by applying the canonical order of the power set \mathcal{P} of $\{1, \dots, p+q\}$, i.e. by using the index set

$$\mathcal{I} := \{\{i_1, \dots, i_s\} \in \mathcal{P} \mid 1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_s \leq p+q\} \quad (4)$$

and then define $e_I := e_{i_1} \dots e_{i_s}$ for all $I \in \mathcal{I}$. Set $e_\emptyset := 1_{\mathbb{R}}$. A general element x of $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$

$$x = \sum_I e_I x_I := \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}} e_I x_I, \quad (x_I \in \mathbb{R}) \quad (5)$$

is termed multivector. The name stems from the fact that for $k \in \{0, \dots, p+q\}$

$$\mathcal{C}_{p,q}^k := \{e_I \mid I \in \mathcal{I}, |I| = k\} \quad (6)$$

spans a linear subspace of $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$ ($\mathcal{C}_{p,q}^0 = \mathbb{R}$, $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}^1 = \mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ and $\sum_k \mathcal{C}_{p,q}^k = \mathcal{C}_{p,q}$). Projection onto subspaces is defined via the grade operator

$$\langle \cdot \rangle_k : \mathcal{C}_{p,q} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}_{p,q}^k, x \mapsto \sum_{\substack{I \in \mathcal{I}, \\ |I|=k}} x_I e_I, \quad (7)$$

with convention $\langle \cdot \rangle := \langle \cdot \rangle_0$ for the so-called scalar part. Projection onto the I -th component (w.r.t. \mathcal{E}) of a multivector, on the other hand, is written as $[\cdot]_I$.

Involutions on $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$ are mappings that when applied twice yield the identity again. Examples are inversion

$$inv(x) := \sum_{k=0}^{p+q} (-1)^k \langle x \rangle_k \quad (8)$$

and reversion

$$rev(x) := \sum_{k=0}^{p+q} (-1)^{\frac{k(k-1)}{2}} \langle x \rangle_k. \quad (9)$$

Combining these two mappings yields the operation of conjugation as it is known for complex numbers and quaternions. The principal involution defined by

$$\tilde{e}_I = rev(e_I) e_0^{[I_q]} \quad (10)$$

is of main importance for us, whereby $[I_q]$ stands for the number of negative signature vector factors in e_I . Note that $\widetilde{\widetilde{xy}} = \widetilde{yx}$. Any non-null vector of $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$ has an inverse (w.r.t. the geometric product) and is an element of the Clifford group.

Definition 2.2 (Clifford group [16]) *The Clifford group associated with the Clifford algebra $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$ is defined by*

$$\Gamma_{p,q} = \{s \in \mathcal{C}_{p,q} \mid \forall x \in \mathbb{R}^{p,q}, s x inv(s)^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{p,q}\}. \quad (11)$$

The action of $\Gamma_{p,q}$ on $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ is an orthogonal automorphism [17] that extends to multivectors due to the bilinearity of the geometric product.

A Clifford algebra is commutative only for $p+q=1$. In what follows we develop the theory of Clifford neural networks based on multiplication of weights from the left side. Clearly, choosing one side or the other is just a formal choice.

3 Clifford Neurons

A Clifford algebra is a generalization of the real numbers. A Clifford neuron should therefore generalize a real neuron. Formally, such a neuron can be introduced as follows. Consider the most common real neuron of perceptron-type with the identity as activation function. This real neuron computes a weighted sum of its inputs x_i according to

$$y = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + \theta. \quad (12)$$

Using instead multivector weights $w_i \in \mathcal{C}_{p,q}$, a multivector threshold $\theta \in \mathcal{C}_{p,q}$ and replacing real multiplication by the geometric product readily turns (12) into a Clifford neuron, which computes a function from $(\mathcal{C}_{p,q})^n$ to $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$. Note that for $\mathcal{C}_{0,0}$, of course, one gets the real neuron back again.

3.1 Basic Clifford Neurons

A Basic Clifford Neuron is the atom of Clifford neural computation.

Definition 3.1 (Basic Clifford Neuron (BCN)) *A Basic Clifford Neuron, $\text{BCN}_{p,q}$, computes the following function from $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$ to $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$*

$$y = w \otimes_{p,q} x + \theta. \quad (13)$$

A BCN has only one multivector input and therefore also only one multivector weight but it does process multidimensional entities (for $p + q > 0$). The general update rule using gradient descent for a BCN with simplified, for notation purposes, error function

$$E = \|\text{error}\|^2 := \|d - y\|^2, \quad (14)$$

where d stands for desired output, reads

$$\Delta w = -\frac{\partial E}{\partial w} = 2\text{error} \tilde{x}. \quad (15)$$

The complete dynamics of a BCN can be derived by an eigenanalysis of its Hessian matrix. The threshold θ of a BCN is a generic parameter in the sense, that it does not depend on the signature (p, q) of the underlying Clifford algebra. In what follows we therefore only study Hessians w.r.t. the multivector weight w .

Theorem 3.2 (Hessian of a BCN) *The elements of the Hessian matrix $\mathbf{H}_{\text{BCN}_{p,q}}$ of a $\text{BCN}_{p,q}$ are given by*

$$\partial_{IJ} E = \partial_{JI} E = \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_J \partial w_I} = 2 \langle \tilde{e}_I e_J x \tilde{x} \rangle \quad (16)$$

where $\tilde{\cdot}$ denotes principal involution.

A proof of this theorem can be found in [7]. The theorem states that for every I, J the scalar component of the product resulting from multiplying $\tilde{e}_I e_J$ with the multivector $x \tilde{x}$ is "picked out". Consequently, one gets easily the following result for the neurons $\text{BCN}_{0,q}$.

Corollary 3.3 *The Hessian of a $\text{BCN}_{0,q}$ is a scalar matrix aE , where E denotes the identity matrix.*

This means that the error surface of a $\text{BCN}_{0,q}$ is isotropic. Hence batch learning converges in one step if the optimal learning rate is used. Note that both the case of the complex $\text{BCN}_{0,1}$ and the case of the quaternionic $\text{BCN}_{0,2}$ are covered by the corollary.

We now have a closer look at the $\text{BCN}_{0,1}$ and the $\text{BCN}_{1,0}$.

It is well known that complex multiplication is equivalent to a rotation and a scaling [18]. Hence the whole propagation function of a $\text{BCN}_{0,1}$ can be illustrated as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Illustration of the propagation function of the complex $\text{BCN}_{0,1}$.

A typical error surface of a $\text{BCN}_{0,1}$ is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Typical error surface of the complex $\text{BCN}_{0,1}$.

The matrix representation of a multivector $x = x_0 + x_1e_1 \in \mathcal{C}_{1,0}$ of unit norm has matrix representation [10]

$$x = \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon \cosh(\phi) & \epsilon \sinh(\phi) \\ \epsilon \sinh(\phi) & \epsilon \cosh(\phi) \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

for some $\phi \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\epsilon = \pm 1$. Hence multiplication in $\mathcal{C}_{1,0}$ is equivalent to a hyperbolic rotation and a scaling. The resulting propagation function of a $\text{BCN}_{1,0}$ is illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3: Illustration of the propagation function of the hyperbolic $BCN_{1,0}$.

The error surface of a $BCN_{1,0}$ is not isotropic. It is characterized by elliptic contour lines which are rotated about 45 degrees w.r.t. the origin (see figure 4). This follows directly from (16).

Figure 4: Typical error surface of the hyperbolic $BCN_{1,0}$.

In general, the propagation function of a BCN is not equivalent to a (not necessarily Euclidean) rotation, scaling and translation. Such a decomposition, however, can be realized by a second type of Clifford neuron.

3.2 Spinor Clifford Neurons

A Spinor Clifford Neuron (SCN) mimics the action of the Clifford group. Note again that the Clifford group acts on entities of any grade (not only vectors).

Definition 3.4 For $p, q \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $p + q > 1$ a Spinor Clifford Neuron, $SCN_{p,q}$, computes the following function from $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$ to $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$

$$y = w x \phi(w) + \theta, \quad (18)$$

where ϕ denotes a particular involution (e.g. inversion, reversion,...).

The prototype of a SCN is the quaternionic SCN based on conjugation. A SCN has also only one independent weight though a two-sided multiplication takes place. For a SCN with (adapted) error function (14) gradient descent therefore results in a two-stage update procedure. First compute the update of the "right weight" in (18) as

$$w_R := \widetilde{(w x)} \text{ error} \quad (19)$$

which then yields $\Delta w = \phi(w_R)$.

Unfortunately, the Hessian of a SCN does have a rather complicated form.

Theorem 3.5 (Hessian of a SCN) *The elements of the Hessian matrix $\mathbf{H}_{\text{SCN}_{p,q}}$ of a SCN are given by*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial E}{\partial w_J \partial w_I} = & \quad 2 \langle (e_J x \bar{w} + w x \bar{e}_J) (e_I x \bar{w} + w x \bar{e}_I) \widetilde{} \rangle \\ & - 2 \langle (d - w x \bar{w}) (e_I x \bar{e}_J + e_J x \bar{e}_I) \widetilde{} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $\widetilde{(\cdot)}$ stands for the involution of the SCN.

A proof of this theorem is given in [7]. If w is of small absolute value the approximation $\mathbf{H}_{\text{SCN}_{p,q}} \approx 2 \cdot \mathbf{H}_{\text{BCN}_{p,q}}$ holds.

4 Clifford Multi-layer Perceptrons

The real-valued Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) is the prototype of a feed-forward neural network and has found uncountable applications in many different fields. Its computational power is determined by the nonlinear activation function that is applied in all of its single neurons. Clifford-valued MLPs can be based on either the BCN (Clifford MLP) or the SCN (Spinor Clifford MLP).

There are many suitable activation functions for the real-valued MLP, with tanh and the logistic function being the two most popular choices. It is possible to apply such a suitable real-valued activation function g to every component in a Clifford neuron. For a Clifford MLP the output of the j -th neuron in the l -th layer then reads

$$\sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}} g^{(l)} \left(\sum_k (w_{kj}^{(l)} \otimes_{p,q,r} x_k^{(l-1)} + \theta_j^{(l)})_I \right) e_I, \quad (21)$$

where $x_k^{(l-1)}$ denotes the k -th input from the previous layer. The drawback of these so-called component-wise activation functions is that they do not allow to (further) process all correlations of data (a more detailed explanation for the complex and quaternionic case in the context of ICA can be found in [13] and [3], respectively). While this is surely a limitation, the Clifford MLP with component-wise activation function is still of the same universal computational power as the real-valued MLP (see sub-section 4.1).

The desirable alternative to component-wise activation functions are so-called fully activation functions, which are Clifford-valued. Since MLPs are usually trained by gradient descent w.r.t. the weights (back-propagation algorithm), these functions should be differentiable w.r.t. to the underlying Clifford algebra.

The best understood fully activation functions are those of the complex domain. Unfortunately, every entire (complex differentiable everywhere) bounded function is constant by Liouville's theorem. Consequently, fully complex activation functions are unbounded, which is an undesired attribute [9]. Moreover, such functions have singularities in which they are not continuous. This is illustrated for the complex tanh function in figure 5. A complete discussion of fully complex functions can be found in the work of Kim & Adali (see e.g. [12]).

Figure 5: Plot of the complex tanh function. Real part (left) and imaginary part (right).

4.1 Universal Approximation

Universal approximation, though being a rather abstract mathematical concept, is of great importance for the theory of neural computation [14]. Universal approximation guarantees that a network (more precisely a certain family of networks) can theoretically approximate well any kind of function out of a given class of functions. Simply put, this property deals with the theoretical existence of a solution to a given type of learning problem. The precise notion of universal approximation reads

Definition 4.1 (Universal Approximator) *Let F and L be two families of functions of a normed space (X, p) . Let d be the metric induced by the norm p . Then F is said to be an universal approximator for L in the norm p if, for any $l \in L$ and any $\epsilon > 0$, there exists some $f \in F$ such that $d(l, f) < \epsilon$. If additionally $L = (X, p)$, then F is said to be dense in (X, p) .*

Note that universal approximation is always meant w.r.t. some norm. Hence it makes no sense to speak of universal approximation without providing such a frame of reference. There are basically two types of norms, namely the L_p norms ($1 \leq p < \infty$)

$$\|f\|_p = \left(\int_X |f(x)|^p dx \right)^{1/p} \quad (22)$$

and the L_∞ norm (supremum norm)

$$\|f\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in X} |f(x)|. \quad (23)$$

L_p norms are associated with discontinuous functions while the supremum norm is associated with continuous functions. There is hardly any need for real-valued MLPs with discontinuous activation functions in the framework of general function approximation. Hence

Theorem 4.2 (Cybenko [8]) *For any continuous function g which does fulfill $\lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} g(x) = 0$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} g(x) = 1$ finite sums of the form*

$$S_\infty = \sum_{j=1}^N \lambda_j g(y_j^T x + \theta_j) \quad (24)$$

are dense in $C([0, 1]^n)$ with respect to L_∞ .

is the most important practical result for real-valued MLPs. Moreover, in its seminal paper Cybenko did prove that for discontinuous but measurable activation functions universal approximation holds w.r.t. L_p norms.

Theorem 4.2 extends to the case of Clifford MLPs with component-wise activation function, which means that finite sums of the form

$$M_\infty := \sum_{j=1}^N \lambda_j \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}} g\left(\sum_k (w_{kj} \otimes_{p,q} x_k + \theta_j)_I\right) e_I \quad (25)$$

are dense in $C(\mathcal{C}_{p,q}^n, \mathcal{C}_{p,q})$ w.r.t. L_∞ as long as g fulfills (24) [6]. For Spinor Clifford MLPs this has so far only been proven for the quaternionic case [5].

On the other hand, it has been shown in [2] that for the complex logistic function universal approximation w.r.t. the supremum norm L_∞ does not hold. For fully complex activation functions (which are discontinuous) universal approximation does hold w.r.t. L_p norms, where p depends on the type of singularity of the function [12].

To summarize, some care has to be taken when using fully activation functions in Clifford MLPs. Fully activation functions have higher representation capabilities than component-wise ones. This, however, cannot be demonstrated by using the framework of universal approximation.

4.2 Back-propagation Algorithm

In this section we derive the back-propagation algorithm for a Clifford MLP with arbitrary underlying algebra $\mathcal{C}_{p,q}$. We start with the derivation in case of a component-wise activation function g . This has been carried out first in [6]. Complex back-propagation has been first published in [15], the quaternionic algorithm originates from [1].

First define the activation of the j -th node in the l -th layer

$$s_j^{(l)} := \sum_k w_{kj}^{(l)} \otimes_{p,q,r} x_k^{(l)} + \theta_j^{(l)}, \quad (26)$$

and the output of that node

$$y_j^{(l)} := \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}} g([s_j^{(l)}]_I) e_I. \quad (27)$$

The (simplified) sum-of-squares error function then reads

$$E := \frac{1}{2} \|d - y\|, \quad (28)$$

whereby $y = (y_1^{(L)}, y_2^{(L)}, \dots)$ is the vector of the single outputs. Starting at the output layer, we have to compute

$$\nabla E_{w_{kj}^{(L)}} = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\partial E}{\partial [w_{kj}^{(L)}]_I} e_I. \quad (29)$$

Applying the chain rule to each term of (29) yields

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial [w_{kj}^{(L)}]_I} = \sum_{B \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\partial E}{\partial [s_j^{(L)}]_B} \frac{\partial [s_j^{(L)}]_B}{\partial [w_{kj}^{(L)}]_I}. \quad (30)$$

The two terms of the RHS of (30) can be computed separately. For a single partial derivative of the error function with respect to the node activation we obtain

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial [s_j^{(L)}]_B} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial [y_j]_B} \frac{\partial [y_j]_B}{\partial [s_j^{(L)}]_B} \quad (31)$$

$$= ([d_j]_B - [y_j]_B) \cdot (g^{(L)})'([s_j^{(L)}]_B), \quad (32)$$

and hence

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{B \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\partial E}{\partial [s_j^{(L)}]_B} &= ([d_j]_B - [y_j]_B) \\ &\cdot (g^{(L)})'([s_j^{(L)}]_B) e_B \\ &=: \delta_j^{(L)}. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

For updating the weights in a hidden layer l we have to compute analogously to (29)

$$\nabla E_{w_{kj}^{(l)}} = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\partial E}{\partial [w_{kj}^{(l)}]_I} e_I, \quad (34)$$

yielding now

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial [w_{kj}^{(l)}]_I} = \sum_{B \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\partial E}{\partial [s_j^{(l)}]_B} \frac{\partial [s_j^{(l)}]_B}{\partial [w_{kj}^{(l)}]_I}. \quad (35)$$

Comparing (35) with (30) we see that the only remaining task is the computation of the new error terms $\frac{\partial E}{\partial [s_j^{(l)}]_B}$, which now involves the error terms from the $(l+1)$ -th layer. The complete back-propagation algorithm then reads

$$\Delta w_{kj}^{(l)} = \delta_j^{(l)} \otimes_{p,q} \widetilde{(y_k^{(l-1)})} \quad (36a)$$

$$\Delta \theta_j^{(l)} = \delta_j^{(l)}, \quad (36b)$$

with

$$\delta_j^{(l)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}} (g^{(L)})' (d_j - y_j^{(L)})_I e_I & \text{if } l = L, \\ \sum_{I \in \mathcal{I}} (g^{(l)})' (\sum_m \widetilde{(w_{jm}^{(l+1)})}) \otimes_{p,q} \delta_m^{(l+1)} e_I & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

For MLPs with fully activation function G only the error term has to be modified [4]

$$\delta_j^{(l)} = \begin{cases} \widetilde{(G^{(L)})'} (d_j - y_j^{(L)}) & \text{if } l = L, \\ \widetilde{(G^{(l)})'} (\sum_m \widetilde{(w_{jm}^{(l+1)})}) \otimes_{p,q} \delta_m^{(l+1)} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

The back-propagation algorithm for the Quaternionic Spinor Clifford can be found in [5].

References

- [1] P. Arena, L. Fortuna, G. Muscato, and M. G. Xibilia. *Neural Networks in Multidimensional Domains*. Number 234 in LNCIS. Springer-Verlag, 1998.
- [2] P. Arena, L. Fortuna, R. Re, and M. G. Xibilia. Multilayer perceptrons to approximate complex valued functions. *International Journal of Neural Systems*, 6:435–446, 1995.
- [3] N. Le Bihan and Sven Buchholz. Quaternionic independent component analysis using hypercomplex nonlinearities. In *IMA 7th Conference on Mathematics in Signal Processing*, Cirencester, UK, 2006.
- [4] S. Buchholz. A Theory of Neural Computation with Clifford Algebras. Technical Report Number 0504, Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, Institut für Informatik und Praktische Mathematik, May 2005.
- [5] S. Buchholz and G. Sommer. Quaternionic Spinor MLP. In *8th European Symposium on Artificial Neural Networks, ESANN 2000, Bruges*, pages 377–382, 2000.
- [6] S. Buchholz and G. Sommer. Clifford Algebra Multilayer Perceptrons. In G. Sommer, editor, *Geometric Computing with Clifford Algebra*, pages 315–334. Springer-Verlag, Heidelberg, 2001.
- [7] S. Buchholz, K. Tachibana, and E. Hitzer. Optimal learning rates for clifford neurons. In *International Conference on Artificial Neural Networks*, volume 1, pages 864–873, Porto, Portugal, 9-13 September 2007.
- [8] G. Cybenko. Approximation by superposition of a sigmoidal function. *Mathematics of Control, Signals and Systems*, 2:303–314, 1989.
- [9] G. Georgiou and C. Koutsougeras. Complex domain backpropagation. *IEEE Trans. on Circuits and Systems II*, 39(5):330–334, 1992.
- [10] W. Hein. *Struktur- und Darstellungstheorie der klassischen Gruppen*. Springer-Verlag, 1990.
- [11] A. Hirose. *Complex-Valued Neural Networks*. Number 32 in Studies in Computational Intelligence. Springer-Verlag, 2006.
- [12] T. Kim and T. Adali. Approximation by fully-complex multilayer perceptrons. *Neural Networks*, 15(7):1641–1666, 2003.
- [13] T. Kim, T. Adali, and V. D. Calhoun. Independent component analysis by complex nonlinearities. In *Proc. ICASSP*, Montreal, Canada, 2004.
- [14] V. Kurkova. Kolmogorov’s theorem and multilayer neural networks. *Neural Networks*, 5(3):501–506, 1992.
- [15] H. Leung and S. Haykin. The complex backpropagation algorithm. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, 3(9):2101–2104, 1991.
- [16] P. Lounesto. *Clifford Algebras and Spinors*. Cambridge University Press, 1997.

- [17] I. R. Porteous. *Clifford Algebras and the Classical Groups*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1995.
- [18] I. M. Yaglom. *Complex Numbers in Geometry*. Academic Press, New York, 1968.

S. Buchholz, K. Tachibana, E. Hitzer, Introduction to Theory, Construction and Application of Clifford Neural Networks, ICONIP 2007, 14th International Conf. on Neural Information Processing, Japan, 13 Nov. 2007, 14 pp.